

"THE ESSENCE OF INTERACTIVE EDUCATION IN MODERN EDUCATION"

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Annotation: In this article, modern education and its teaching process in today's 21st century ICT era, the results of this modern education and their achievements for today's young generation, from the perspective of creative, integrative and society, are discussed. is conducted.

Key words: Integration, computer, development, society, pedagogue, creative, science and innovation, continuity, consistency and diversity, future, foundation, traditional lesson.

Modern education is the latest and most modern version of education taught in schools and educational institutions in the 21st century. Modern education, modern education is not only in the classroom, but also in the fields of commerce, science and art. . Modern teaching also uses the latest technologies, such as techniques, ICT, slides, e-books, films, to provide knowledge to students and make the learning process more interesting.

Education is an activity of cooperation between the teacher and students, and it is in this process that the development of a person, his education and upbringing are formed. As time changes, demands and obligations are increasing day by day. After all, the 21st century is the time when technologies and digital innovations are developed, the education system and teaching activities cannot remain in their place as a whole. Now we need to bring modernity to the education system, change it in every aspect, be free from uniformity, use information technologies. In the lessons, the teacher conveys his knowledge, skills and abilities to the students through exercises, exhibitions, and methods. If the teacher uses different interactive

methods and methods in the delivery process, the student learning that lesson learns to use different forms of learning, as well as receiving, processing and applying the information he is learning. one of the main goals of modern education is to grow and develop the student's ability to think freely, to ensure that his speech is fluent and clear. The purpose of education is formed according to the needs of society. And in modern study, teaching develops in accordance with that formed education. The goal of education in scientific literature is to create skills and competencies, to develop logical and creative thinking. , increasing communicative literacy, inculcating the national idea, forming oriental education, spiritual enrichment of the individual. The implementation of advanced pedagogical and new information technologies in education, in addition to increasing the effectiveness of educational activities, is of great importance in educating an independent and logically thinking, well-rounded and highly moral person by applying scientific achievements in life. in the process, the pedagogue has a great responsibility. Third, in this regard, the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, emphasizes the following words: "In order for an educator to become a teacher, to cultivate the intelligence of others, to enjoy the benefits of enlightenment, to grow up as a true patriot, a true citizen first of all, the educator must meet such high requirements and have such great qualities.

In the modern teaching process, the interest in the use of interactive methods and information technologies, exhibitions in the educational process is increasing day by day. One of the reasons for this is that until now, in traditional education, students were taught only to acquire basic knowledge, and it was limited to simplicity, and the use of modern technologies allows them to search for the acquired knowledge themselves and express their opinion on that topic. learns to receive, analyze, and even draw final conclusions by themselves. In this process, the teacher, pedagogue creates conditions for personal development, formation, learning and upbringing, increases creativity and personal motivation. Today, in the course of modern education: "Brainstorming", "Thoughtstorming", various

presentation methods, "Sinquain", "BBB", If the main tools of the teaching process with a high methodical aspect, such as "Five plus", "6x6x6", debate, role-playing games, FSMU, are used at the right time and in their place, they will definitely give a great result. It is also a strange news that in the past, our scholars tried to remind us of the educational system of that time, that is, the Mozag system. - it is like a child walking from one garden to another. That is, you used a method in some subject and took the children from the environment (garden) before the method to another environment (garden). When choosing educational methods, it is appropriate to choose based on the didactic task of each lesson. The main basis of modern education is to organize the lesson process with methods that activate the activities of different districts and learners while preserving the traditional lesson form. For this, the lesson process should be organized rationally, the teacher should know the interest of the learners and encourage their activity in the educational process, divide the educational material into small pieces and use various methods to reveal their content. it would be appropriate to use it.

In conclusion, it can be said that the main foundation of our time is education, the black eyes of the young generation watching the high tides, the education process, studies, and the future of today's innocent children who are happy about everything. in the hands of today's pedagogues, they should be able to demonstrate modern education, today's demands, high goals, "the beauty of various gardens". The main basis of our modern education is interactive methods, organizes various mind-blowing tools and exhibitions.

References:

1. Tolipov.V.K., Sharipov.Sh.S. "Pedagogical foundations of the development of creative activity of the student's personality ".-T, "Fan" publishing house, 2012.
2. R. Mavlonova, O. Torayev, K. Khalikberdiyev. "PEDAGOGY" requirements of the faculties of primary education methodology of higher educational institutions of the republic, a textbook for students of pedagogic lyceums and colleges /_ Tashkent: Teacher "2000.